

Analysis of Culture-Specific Items and Translation Errors in Translating Bankim Chandra's Novel 'Anandamath' by Sri Aurobindo.

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Cultural references in source texts can be the trickiest part of translation, as they involve choosing the right words and understanding the culture behind them. Translation studies all over the world are experiencing a cultural revolution in all its senses as never before. Translation of Culture-specific items has been and still remains one of the topical issues. The aim of this study is to explore how Culture-Specific items (CSI) have been translated (Foreignization or domestication) by Sri Aurobindo While translating Bankim's novel 'Anandamath'. This overarching aim was divided into two specific objectives: Identifying how Aurobindo translated Culture-specific items in Anandamath and is there any translation errors made by the translator. Newmark's (2010) categorization of culture-specific items was adopted in order to classify the culture-specific items and Davie's (2003) strategies for Culture-specific items translation.

Keywords: Culture-specific items, Anandamath, Translation Error, Foreignization, Domestication.

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